

EFFECT OF GRAPHENE NANOPATELET THICKNESS AND CONCENTRATION ON THE TENSILE PROPERTIES OF EPOXY RESIN

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Keywords: Resin-based nanocomposites, Graphene nanoplatelets, Fracture toughness, Tensile properties.

ABSTRACT

The effect of graphene nanoplatelets addition on the mechanical and fracture characteristics of the resulting polymer nanocomposites is investigated. For the preparation of the materials, the system of epoxy resin SR 8100 and hardener SD 8824 was used. Two types of exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets (GnPs) were used: Grade C-750 and Grade M-15 with thicknesses of 2 and 6 nm, respectively. Initially, GnPs were dispersed within the epoxy resin using a high speed shear mixer followed by a cure cycle recommended for the specific epoxy resin. Following the aforementioned procedure, several tensile specimens were prepared having different GnPs concentrations, namely 0.10, 0.25, 0.50, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0 and 5.0 wt%. The mechanical properties of epoxy/GnPs nanocomposites, such as the ultimate tensile strength and modulus of elasticity were calculated from the respective mechanical test results. The results indicate that the GnPs type and concentration play an important role on the mechanical performance. At low concentrations (< 1.0 wt% GnPs) both the tensile strength and the modulus of elasticity are increased. At higher concentrations (> 5 wt% GnPs), a decrease in all investigated mechanical properties is noticed possibly due to the nanomaterials' agglomeration.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymers have found essential applications in the industry and especially in the fields of aerospace, automotive and electronics. Several innovative polymer nanocomposites reinforced with different types of filler materials that could be at the micron-level, or during the last decade, at the nano-level, have been developed. To this end, different filler materials, e.g. nano-silica [1], [2], carbon nanotubes [3]-[5] or even graphene, e.g. [6]-[11], are reported in the open literature to be used in order to enhance the mechanical properties of the matrix.

Literature on reinforcing epoxy resins with graphene and their effect on cracking and fracture toughness enhancement seems to be limited so far. Rafiee et al [9] investigated the toughness enhancement with different types of nano-fillers and concluded that graphene seems to be the most promising reinforcement type. Qiu et al [12] reported that the graphene nano-reinforced resins demonstrated higher plastic deformations at their fracture surface, when compared to the neat resin. Chateerjee et al [13] also reported that the higher thickness of graphene nanoplatelets essentially increased the fracture toughness of modified resins. On the contrary, the theoretical simulations of Zhao and Hoa [14] showed the exact opposite. More recently, Wang et al [15] and Chandrasekaran et al [16] investigated the toughening mechanism of an epoxy resin reinforced with graphene nanoplatelets. The results have shown that the smaller size of graphene was highly effective in hindering crack propagation.

In the present work, different graphene nanoplatelet types and concentrations were investigated as a reinforcement of a typical epoxy matrix. Light optical microscopy was used to investigate the GnPs dispersion. The effect of both graphene size as well as low and high concentration regimes on the tensile mechanical properties of the matrix were studied. The fracture surfaces of the investigated nano-composites were investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Two types of GnPs were used as reinforcement material in the present study, under the commercial names of xGnP[®] Grade C-750 and xGnP[®] Grade M-15, both supplied by XG Sciences. More specific, GnPs Grade C (with an average thickness of 2 nm and average particle diameter of 2 μm) and GnPs Grade M (with thickness of approximately 6 nm and average particle diameter of 15 μm) were added in different concentrations and dispersed in epoxy resin. Photo-micrographs of the exploited nano-reinforcements are available in the literature [17]. A typical system of epoxy resin SR 8100/hardener SD 8824 supplied from SICOMIN (13161 Chateaufort Martigue Cedex - France) with a very low viscosity at ambient temperature (ratio 100:22 parts per weight) was used as matrix in the present study.

To fabricate the epoxy nanocomposites the GnPs were dispersed in epoxy resin using a high speed shear mixer (Silverson L4RT) at 4000 rpm for 30 min. The mixtures were poured into molds and placed in a vacuum heating oven (Salvis Lab VC-20 Vacucentre Vacuum Oven) at 90 °C for 30 min for degassing. The tensile specimens had a gauge length equal to 50 mm at the reduced cross-section according to the ASTM standard D638 and a 5 mm nominal thickness. The applied curing treatment was carried out at 60 °C for 40 min, followed by post-curing at 60 °C for 4 hours, as recommended by the resin's manufacturer data sheet. Curing was conducted using an electrical oven with ± 0.1 °C temperature control.

A light optical microscope Leica[®] DM-LM equipped with a digital camera was used to obtain microscopic information concerning the surface of the investigated nanocomposites. Their surface was polished ground with #1200 grit SiC paper and subsequently polished with 9 and 3 μm diamond suspension.

Tensile tests were performed according to the ASTM D638 standard at room temperature and the crosshead displacement speed was kept constant, equal to 0.016 mm/min. An MTS Insight electromechanical machine of 10 kN load capacity was used. An appropriate MTS extensometer was attached on the 50 mm gauge length of the tensile specimens, to collect the accurate elongation data of the specimens. The data recorded during the tests were applied force, the grip's displacement as well as the data of the extensometer. The data were recorded and stored in a PC. At least five samples were tested per different experimental batch. In total, more than 75 tensile specimens were tested and evaluated. Tensile modulus of elasticity was calculated from the linear elastic regime of the tensile nominal stress - nominal strain curve.

After the mechanical tests, morphological characterization of the fracture surfaces of the investigated nano-composites was evaluated by optical microscopy as well as LEO 1530 FE-SEM Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Dispersion

Nanofiller dispersion is an important issue as GnPs have a tendency to form agglomerates due to strong van der Waals attraction, large surface areas and p-p interaction. With the increase in nanofiller concentration the dispersion becomes even more challenging. Concerning literature, it is observed that the increase in filler content, e.g. in [5], increases the possibility for agglomeration sites within the composites. Tang et al [18] acknowledged that the poor graphene oxide (GO) dispersion resulted in lower increase in the mechanical properties. Likewise, in [15] it was observed that during curing, the thick GO sheets tend to form agglomerates and therefore their effective thickness increases accordingly.

The achievement of a homogeneous dispersion results to an improvement on the mechanical properties. In [2], it was shown that the low thickness GnPs plays an important role for the efficient dispersion in the matrix, since it increases the possibility to retain the striking in-plane properties of graphene. Images in Figure 1 show the random dispersions of 2 nm low thickness GnPs (Grade C) and 6 nm high thickness GnPs (Grade M) at the same concentration of 2.0 wt% of resin. Comparing the two microscope pictures it is obvious that better dispersion was achieved using the low thickness GnPs.

Figure 1: Microscope photograph of 2.0 wt% GnPs (a) low thickness (2 nm) and (b) high thickness (6 nm) dispersed into the epoxy resin.

3.2 Tensile mechanical properties

The reinforcement effect is a complex issue since it involves parameters of load transfer, stress concentration and defect distribution that in some cases are complementary and in some others are contradictory. Typical engineering stress – strain curves can be seen in Figure 2 for both types of reinforcement and for different concentrations. It is quite evident that with varying GnPs concentration, the tensile mechanical behavior of the nano-reinforced materials changes. For the very low concentrations, it seems that the strength properties increase at the expense of ductility, while the opposite seems to happen for the higher concentration and for the lower thickness (Grade C) nano-reinforcement. For the thicker nano-reinforcement, the higher concentrations decreased considerably the tensile ductility.

Figure 2: Typical tensile curves of nanocomposite resin for the different investigated percentages of (a) low thickness and (b) high thickness GnPs, respectively.

The effect of various concentrations of the two different types of GnPs on the modulus of elasticity is shown in Figure 3a. The results are compared with results from the literature. It is observed that, in general, the addition of low concentrations (< 1.0 % wt GnPs) enhances the elastic modulus of the epoxy resin, as it was concluded also by Li et al [10] and Qiu and Wang [12]. Figure 3a shows that the modulus of elasticity slightly increases with increasing GnPs concentration in the matrix. Similar enhancement can be noticed for various resin matrices reported in the literature as it is concluded from the same figure. Two different regimes are also marked in the diagram, individually separated at approximate 0.75 wt% concentration to denote the two different results of experiments of low (< 1.0 wt%) and high (> 1.0 wt%) concentrations. Results from the open literature confirm the enhancement in modulus of elasticity, especially for the low concentration regime. The small decrease in modulus of elasticity at around 1.0 wt% GnPs was also noticed by Shokrieh et al [19] and Ghaleb et al [20], this might be caused by possible agglomerates of the nano-reinforcement [5], [21].

Figure 3b summarizes the experimental results of the ultimate tensile strength R_m for both nanocomposites. The experimental results are again categorized into low and high concentration regimes and compared with results from the literature. The results of ultimate tensile strength show the same trend with increasing GnPs concentration as it was observed for the modulus of elasticity. A peak in R_m is noticed for the 0.25 wt % concentration and for both investigated types; this enhancement is higher (17.8 %) for the thick type of GnPs and lower (11.3 % increase) for the thin type of GnPs reinforcement. Similar results were presented by Wang et al [22], showing that R_m for the higher thickness GnPs decreased by almost 25 % at 5.0 wt% concentration, while using lower thickness GnPs this decrease was almost negligible. In addition, it was shown [18] that the poor dispersion considerably decreased the ultimate tensile strength. Data extracted from similar nano-reinforced resin matrices by various researchers, e.g. [22]-[25] are also plotted in the same diagram, where this local peak in ultimate tensile strength is also evident.

Figure 3: (a) Modulus of elasticity and (b) ultimate tensile strength of the investigated nanocomposites for different GnPs concentrations.

3.3 Fracture surface analysis

The fracture surfaces of the modified epoxy resins were investigated by SEM and typical images are shown in Figure 4. The neat epoxy resins' fracture surface demonstrates typical brittle fracture characteristics and shows wrinkle-like texture [9] or "river-like" fracture patterns [6] initialized from the cracks (Figure 4 a and b). After its initiation, the crack propagated very rapidly in the matrix, just like in a typical brittle material. This river-like pattern originated from the various micro-cracks that actually were merged/expanded, while the area between these patterns is extremely smooth, showing the high propagation velocity [15]. The GnPs Grade C (low thickness) reinforced epoxy resins' fracture surface also exhibits similar "river-like" fracture patterns, however quite a different fracture morphology is presented (Figure 4c and d). Low magnification image shows that fracture surface seems to be smoother, however the high magnification image (Figure 4d) reveals that high surface roughness was produced. The surface seems to be more ductile and this is evidence that the GnPs

provided obstacles to the rapid crack propagation. Crack branching and subsequent ditching provide evidence for higher crack resistance to micro-cracking and hence, the micro-cracking in order to propagate have to continuously change directions towards to the weakest ligament of the material that is the GnPs/matrix interphase. This continuous change in crack propagation is also evident for the thicker Grade M GnPs (Figure 4e and f), however the larger dimples and ditches confirms the higher cracking propagation rates compared to low thickness GnPs. Hence, lower fracture toughness is expected when using the same filler concentration and thicker GnPs.

Figure 14: Scanning electron microscopic images of fracture surfaces of (a), (b) neat epoxy, (c) and (d) 2.0 wt% low thickness GnPs (Grade C) and (e) and (f) 2.0 wt% high thickness GnPs (Grade M) epoxy nanocomposites at different magnifications.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the present investigation can be summarized as follows:

- The tensile mechanical properties of the nanocomposites are influenced by the low thickness (Grade C) GnPs concentration :
 - for the case of low concentrations (< 1.0 wt% GnPs), increased ultimate tensile strength is achieved,
 - increased ductility is noticed for higher concentrations (up to 3.0 wt% GnPs), and
 - for extreme reinforcement (> 5.0 wt% GnPs) a decrease in all mechanical properties is noticed.
- For the case of GnPs with higher thickness (Grade M), the above mechanisms are valid with the exceptions of smaller increase in the modulus of elasticity as well as continuous decrease in tensile ductility. The latter can be possibly attributed to the larger dimples and ditches observed at the fracture surface compared to the low thickness GnPs.
- According to the SEM results, the incorporation of low thickness GnPs results to a more smooth-ductile surface. Possibly, the low thickness GnPs provide obstacles to the rapid crack propagation. Crack branching and subsequent ditching provide evidence for higher crack resistance to micro-cracking.

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